

EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOCIAL COMPETENCE AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN MATHEMATICS AMONG JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

Maridan A. Cadorna
Mai Rani Khristine A. Zipagan

Saint Ferdinand College- City of Ilagan Campus, City of Ilagan, Isabela, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15905095>

ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between social competence and academic performance in Mathematics among 142 Junior High School (JHS) students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in Sto. Domingo, Quirino, Isabela, for the school year 2024–2025. Grounded in Vygotsky’s Sociocultural Theory and Erikson’s Psychosocial Development Theory, the research explored how students’ social, behavioral, and intrapersonal skills correlate with their performance in Mathematics. Data were gathered through a structured questionnaire comprising 150 items assessing ten core components of social competence—such as active listening, empathy, communication, problem-solving, and emotional regulation—and were supported by students’ Mathematics grades from the first to third quarters. Results revealed that students demonstrated high levels of social competence and achieved a very satisfactory performance in Mathematics, with 28.17% earning outstanding ratings. While no significant differences in social competence were found based on age and sex, a significant difference emerged when grouped by grade level. Similarly, academic performance differed significantly by sex but not by age or grade level. Most notably, a moderate positive correlation between social competence and academic performance in Mathematics was established, suggesting that students with higher social skills tend to perform better academically. The study concludes that integrating social skill development into academic instruction, particularly in Mathematics, enhances student outcomes. It recommends curriculum review, increased parental and stakeholder involvement, teacher training, and the implementation of social skill enhancement programs to support both cognitive and interpersonal development in JHS students.

Keywords: *Social Competence, Academic Performance, Mathematics Achievement, Junior High School Students, Interpersonal Skills*

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a vital role in shaping individuals to become productive members of society. Schools, as institutions of learning, are not merely places for academic instruction but also an environment where students acquire essential life skills. In particular, they serve as venues for the development of social skills and critical competencies necessary for personal and societal growth. Through structured interaction and collaboration, students learn to navigate relationships, resolve conflicts, and critically analyze situations, all of which are essential in their future endeavors.

The significance of schools in fostering social and critical skills is supported by the Republic Act No. 10533, or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, which highlighted the K-12 curriculum's role in preparing students for the demands of the 21st century by focusing on critical thinking, interpersonal skills, and adaptability. This reflects the integral role of schools in ensuring students' comprehensive development. In this context, the relationship between social competence and academic performance has become a crucial area of exploration, particularly in core subjects such as mathematics.

Mathematics, known for its logical and problem-solving nature, often requires individual effort, collaborative learning, and effective communication. Social competence, which encompasses interacting positively with others, managing emotions, and building meaningful relationships, can significantly influence a student's ability to thrive in such a learning environment.

For junior high school students, the development of social competence is particularly vital as they navigate the transitional phase of adolescence. This stage is characterized by increased social interactions and the need to adapt to more complex academic challenges. Understanding how social skills contribute to academic performance in mathematics can provide valuable insights into designing educational strategies that foster both cognitive and social growth.

According to Vygotsky's (1978), Sociocultural Theory learning is deeply embedded in social interactions, where students gain knowledge and skills through collaborative activities and guided participation. Meanwhile, Erikson's (1950) Psychosocial Development Theory identifies the school-age stage as a critical period for students to build confidence and competence in both social and intellectual domains.

Social competence is the behavior that in specific social situations leads to positive or negative interaction with teachers, students, the social environment, and the society at large. It involves possessing the necessary social, emotional, and intellectual skills and behaviors to succeed as a member of society and to adapt successfully in social settings.

Social competence is the broad term used to describe students' social effectiveness including their ability to establish and maintain high-quality, mutually satisfying relationships while avoiding negative treatment or victimization from others. When students experience serious difficulties in peer relations, the development of social competence may be threatened. Rejection or victimization by peers may become a source of significant stress to students, contributing to feelings of loneliness and low self-esteem.

Academic performance is the level of achievement a student attains in their educational activities, typically evaluated through grades, test scores, class participation, and performance tasks. In Mathematics, it is the student's success in applying mathematical concepts. It reflects their problem-solving and critical thinking abilities. Academic competence in Mathematics is essential for success in educational settings and future career paths, particularly in fields that rely heavily on quantitative analysis and critical thinking.

Teachers play a significant role in facilitating the social and academic development of students. When teachers believe in students, the students believe in themselves and this agreement between students and teachers is a significant contributor to the students' success in their academic and social achievement.

According to Eccles and Harold (1993), active involvement of parents in their children's education plays a critical role in the student's academic achievement and success. It has been shown that involving parents in their children's education helps to increase students' self-esteem. The more intensive involvement of parents in their children's education, the more beneficial the achievement effects. Research from the National Coalition for Parent Involvement in Education (2006) shares that no matter their income or background, students with involved parents are more likely to have higher grades and test scores, attend school regularly, have better social skills, show improved behavior, and adapt well to school.

Social competence is often a powerful predictor of academic achievement. Students who are accepted by their peers and display responsible forms of behavior at school tend to be high achievers, whereas socially rejected and aggressive students appear to be especially at risk for academic failure.

In the case of Sto. Domingo Integrated School, the researcher has observed that students who actively participate in group activities, maintain positive relationships with peers and teachers, and exhibit effective communication skills often perform better academically, particularly in subjects requiring collaboration and critical thinking like mathematics. Conversely, learners who struggle with social interactions or experience challenges in developing interpersonal relationships often face difficulties in academic engagement and achievement. These experiences highlight the interconnectedness of social competence and academic performance, emphasizing the need for schools to prioritize both.

By observing the interplay between educational practices and these skill sets within the context of Sto. Domingo Integrated School, this research seeks to contribute to the broader understanding of education as a transformative force in individuals' lives and society.

Social and academic competence is greatly significant in the development of students. Junior High School students must be knowledgeable and develop socially as they enter Senior High school so that they can reach their goals and careers in the future. Hence, the writer was prompted to undertake this study.

Research Questions

This study aims to investigate the relationship between social competence and academic performance in Mathematics among Junior High School Students at Sto. Domingo Integrated School during the school year 2024-2025. This study may provide valuable insights into how enhancing social competence could potentially improve academic outcomes in mathematics, guiding educators and policymakers in developing strategies to support both social and academic development.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. sex
 - b. age
 - c. grade level?
2. What is the level of social competence of JHS students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in terms of:
 - A. Social Skills
 - a Active Listening
 - b. Empathy
 - c. Communication
 - d. Cooperation
 - B. Behavioral Skills
 - a. Problem Solving
 - b. Respect
 - c. Conflict Resolution
 - C. Intrapersonal Skills
 - a. Emotional Regulation
 - b. Self-Awareness
 - c. Flexibility
3. Is there a significant difference in the social competence of JHS students when grouped according to their profile?
4. What is the academic performance of JHS students in Mathematics based on their average grade?
5. Is there a significant difference in the academic performance of JHS students when grouped according to their profile?

6. Is there a significant relationship between social competence and academic performance in Mathematics among JHS students at Sto. Domingo Integrated School?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study made use of the descriptive correlation method of research. It is a methodological approach used to identify and describe the relationship between two or more variables primarily focusing on observing, describing, and analyzing how variables naturally co-exist and whether changes in one variable are associated with changes in another. This method applies to the present study as it is ideal for examining natural relationships without manipulating variables and exploring the association between social competence and academic performance in Mathematics among Junior High School students.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in Sto. Domingo Integrated School, located at Sto. Domingo, Quirino, Isabela, a rural town renowned for its scenic landscapes and agricultural lands. The school serves as a key educational institution in the area, providing quality education from kindergarten through Grade 12. It was improved and converted into integrated in 2005 and continues to play a pivotal role in the academic development of students in the community. Sto. Domingo Integrated School is committed to fostering both academic excellence and personal growth, offering a wide range of programs and activities to support the development of its students. As a public institution, the school is accessible to a diverse student body, including those from farming families and other rural sectors. This diverse student population provides a unique perspective on how social competence and academic performance are developed in different social and economic contexts. The school's facilities include well-equipped classrooms, a library, a computer lab, and a science laboratory, which support various learning activities. Despite being located in a rural area, Sto. Domingo Integrated School has continuously adapted to educational innovations, integrating technology and modern teaching methods to enhance learning experiences. The school's environment is conducive to both academic achievement and the development of interpersonal skills, making it an ideal setting for exploring the relationship between social competence and academic performance in mathematics. The study utilized this setting to understand how the school's practices and the involvement of teachers, parents, and peers contribute to students' social and academic growth.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents of this study are the 142 Junior High School students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School from grades 7 to 10 who are officially enrolled during the school year 2024-2025. The table shows the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1 shows the frequency distribution of the respondents per grade level.

Table 1
Frequency Distribution of the Respondents

Grade Level	Frequency
Grade 7	45
Grade 8	37
Grade 9	28
Grade 10	32
Total:	142

Data Gathering Procedure

Permission to conduct the study was first sought from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) through the school principal. After permission was granted, the researcher distributed the questionnaires to the respondents to assess their social competence.

The researcher also requested the mathematics teacher of grades 7 to 10 to allow her to look into the respondents' grades, as permitted by the school principal.

After all relevant data were obtained, these were compiled, organized, analyzed, and interpreted.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data gathered, the following statistical tools were employed:

Frequency and Percentage Count. The academic performance and profile of the students were analyzed using the frequency and percentage count.

Weighted Mean. The student's perception of their social competence was analyzed using the weighted mean.

ANOVA. This was used to determine whether there were significant differences in students' mathematics performance and social competence when grouped according to their profile using a 5% level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Pearson's r test. This was used to determine the degree to which social competence and academic performance in mathematics are related.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:

a. Sex

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Students in Terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	76	53.52
Female	66	46.48
Total	142	100.00

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of students based on their sex.

Data shows that there are 76 male students, which accounts for 53.52% of the total population, and there are 66 female students, representing 46.48%. This reveals that the male population is slightly higher than the female population. The data shows a more diverse and inclusive learning environment, where both male and female students have similar opportunities for social and academic growth and development.

b. Age

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Students According to Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
12-13	58	40.85
14-15	68	47.89
16-17	16	11.27
Total	142	100.00

Table 3 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of students based on age.

The majority of the students fall within the 14–15 age group, with 68 students, accounting for 47.89% of the total. The 12–13 age group follows with 58 students, representing 40.85%, while the 16–17 age group has the fewest students, with only 16, making up 11.27% of the total.

Most students are within the expected age range for junior high school, with the highest concentration in the 14–15 age group. The lower number of students aged 16–17 may indicate that older students may have moved on to senior high school.

c. Grade Level

Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Students in Terms of Grade Level

Grade Level	Frequency	Percentage
7	45	31.69
8	37	26.06
9	28	19.72
10	32	22.54
Total	142	100.00

Table 4 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of students based on their grade level.

Grade 7 has the highest number of students, with 45 individuals making up 31.69% of the total, while Grade 9 has the lowest number, with 28 students, or 19.72%.

The data shows that as the students progress to higher grades, the number declines. The reasons gathered for this decline include dropouts, transfers, and academic challenges leading to retention. The lower number of Grade 9 students indicate an irregular enrollment pattern in previous years.

2. What is the level of social competence among the JHS students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in terms of:

Social Skills

A. Active Listening

Table 5
The Level of Social Competence of JHS Students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in Terms of Active Listening

Active Listening	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
1. I pay full attention when my teacher explains a lesson.	3.35	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
2. I avoid interrupting my classmates during class	2.92	Agree	High social competence

discussions.			
3. I ask questions to clarify instructions given by my teacher.	2.98	Agree	High social competence
4. I can summarize what my peers shared during a group activity.	3.02	Agree	High social competence
5. I use eye contact when listening to my teacher or classmates.	3.25	Agree	High social competence
6. I avoid distractions like using my phone while listening in class.	2.89	Agree	High social competence
7. I nod or use gestures to show I am listening during discussions.	3.09	Agree	High social competence
8. I can remember key points from a lesson or class discussion.	2.87	Agree	High social competence
9. I listen without criticizing others' ideas in group work.	2.91	Agree	High social competence
10. I wait for my teacher to finish speaking before responding.	3.28	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
11. I encourage my classmates to speak by showing interest in their ideas.	3.01	Agree	High social competence
12. I understand the non-verbal cues my teacher uses during class discussions.	3.18	Agree	High social competence
13. I stay focused even during long explanations.	3.26	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
14. I make my classmates feel heard when they share their ideas.	3.08	Agree	High social competence
15. I value the contributions of all group members in discussions.	3.25	Agree	High social competence
Grand Mean	3.10	Agree	High social competence

Table 5 presents the level of social competence of junior high school students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in terms of active listening. The statement, *“I pay full attention when my teacher explains a lesson,”* got the highest weighted mean of 3.35, described as Strongly Agree, indicating very high social competence in this area. The statement, *“I can remember key points from a lesson or class discussion,”* had the lowest weighted mean of 2.87, meaning the students Agree, to the statement, showing that students generally demonstrate good active listening skills.

The grand mean of 3.10 reflects an overall description of “Agree” which signifies high social competence among the students. Data also shows that students have developed effective active listening skills, which contribute to better communication and engagement in academic settings.

B. Empathy

Table 6
The Level of Social Competence of JHS Students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in Terms of Empathy

Empathy	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
1. I understand how my classmates feel when they struggle with Math tasks.	3.28	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
2. I imagine myself in a peer's position when they face difficulties in Mathematics subject.	3.10	Agree	High social competence
3. I offer support to a classmate who feels excluded.	3.18	Agree	High social competence
4. I notice when a classmate is upset, even if they don't say anything.	3.02	Agree	High social competence
5. I try to see things from my teacher's perspective during challenging lessons in Mathematics.	3.04	Agree	High social competence
6. I avoid judging my classmates for their emotions during group work.	3.04	Agree	High social competence
7. I listen when a friend shares their problems in Mathematics tasks.	3.33	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence.

8. I offer comfort to peers who are sad or worried about Mathematics activities.	3.11	Agree	High social competence
9. I am aware of how my words and actions affect my classmates.	3.17	Agree	High social competence
10. I feel happy for my classmates when they succeed academically.	3.34	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
11. I respect my classmates' feelings, even if I don't agree with them.	3.15	Agree	High social competence
12. I am patient with classmates who struggle emotionally in class.	3.09	Agree	High social competence
13. I celebrate the achievements of others in class genuinely.	3.13	Agree	High social competence
14. I feel motivated to help a classmate in distress.	3.12	Agree	High social competence
15. I appreciate how others might experience the same situation differently.	3.12	Agree	High social competence
Grand Mean	3.15	Agree	High social competence

Table 6 presents the level of social competence among junior high school students at Sto. Domingo Integrated School in terms of empathy. It analyzes students' ability to understand, share, and respond to the feelings of others, particularly in academic settings. The highest-rated statement, "I feel happy for my classmates when they succeed academically," received a 3.34 weighted mean, categorized as Strongly Agree, indicating very high social competence. However, some areas, such as noticing when a classmate is upset even if they do not express it, received slightly lower weighted mean of 3.02, suggesting that while students are empathetic, there are still opportunities to strengthen their awareness and response to others' feelings.

The grand mean of 3.15 corresponds to an "Agree" rating, indicating that students generally exhibit high social competence in empathy. Most students recognize their classmates' emotions and provide support when needed, such as offering comfort and avoiding judgment.

C. Communication

Table 7
The Level of Social Competence of JHS Students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in Terms of Communication

Communication	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
1. I can clearly explain my ideas during class discussions.	3.04	Agree	High social competence
2. I use respectful words when talking to my teachers.	3.34	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
3. I adjust my tone depending on whether I'm speaking to teachers or peers.	3.30	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
4. I use positive body language when sharing my thoughts in class.	3.08	Agree	High social competence
5. I can calmly handle misunderstandings with classmates.	3.03	Agree	High social competence
6. I confidently present ideas in front of the class.	2.85	Agree	High social competence
7. I explain lessons or tasks in more than one way if needed.	2.90	Agree	High social competence
8. I avoid dominating conversations during group work.	3.04	Agree	High social competence
9. I listen carefully to understand before responding to a question.	3.34	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
10. I use examples to make my points clearer in group discussions.	3.29	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
11. I engage in polite conversations even when classmates disagree with me.	3.06	Agree	High social competence
12. I remain polite when talking to my classmates during disagreements.	2.98	Agree	High social competence
13. I can adapt my communication style based on the audience.	3.04	Agree	High social competence

14. I ensure everyone gets a chance to speak during group activities.	3.32	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
15. I avoid using inappropriate language in any school setting.	3.04	Agree	High social competence
Grand Mean	3.11	Agree	High social competence

Table 7 presents the level of social competence of junior high school students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in terms of communication. It shows students' ability to express themselves clearly, listen attentively, and engage respectfully in discussions. The statements *"I use respectful words when talking to my teachers,"* and *"I listen carefully to understand before responding to a question"* have a weighted mean of 3.34, indicating a very high level of communication skills. Some aspects, such as confidently presenting ideas in front of the class, received slightly lower ratings of 2.85. This indicates that while students communicate effectively, there may still be a need to develop confidence in expressing complex ideas and adapting their explanations to different contexts.

The grand mean of 3.11 suggests that students generally exhibit high social competence in communication. Developing social competence, particularly in communication, is essential for personal success, making it a crucial area for development among Junior High School students at Sto. Domingo Integrated School.

D. Cooperation

Table 8
The Level of Social Competence of JHS Students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in Terms of Cooperation

Cooperation	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
1. I work well with classmates during group projects.	3.37	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
2. I share responsibilities equally in Math tasks.	3.17	Agree	High social competence
3. I respect the opinions of my classmates during group work.	3.30	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
4. I value the input of every group member.	3.17	Agree	High social competence
5. I avoid dominating discussions during group activities.	3.10	Agree	High social competence

6. I support my classmates when they need help with Math tasks.	3.20	Agree	High social competence
7. I adjust my role based on the group's needs.	3.15	Agree	High social competence
8. I remain positive, even when group work is challenging.	3.20	Agree	High social competence
9. I help resolve disagreements in the group respectfully.	3.09	Agree	High social competence
10. I follow through on tasks assigned to me during group activities.	3.20	Agree	High social competence
11. I avoid blaming others when group work fails.	2.98	Agree	High social competence
12. I encourage classmates who seem shy to participate in group works.	3.11	Agree	High social competence
13. I celebrate my group's success, even if my ideas weren't chosen.	3.01	Agree	High social competence
14. I am willing to compromise for the success of the group.	3.27	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
15. I handle disagreements in group work calmly and respectfully.	3.17	Agree	High social competence
Grand Mean	3.17	Agree	High social competence

Table 8 presents the level of social competence of junior high school students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in terms of cooperation. The statement, "*I work well with classmates during group projects,*" has a weighted mean of 3.37, suggesting that students are highly engaged in teamwork and collaboration. Statements such as "*I avoid blaming others when group work fails*" received slightly lower means of 2.98, indicating that some students struggle with accountability.

The majority of students are able to handle group disagreements calmly and respectfully, as reflected in a mean score of 3.17 for this aspect. These finding shows that while cooperation is generally well-practiced, there is still room for growth. Fostering an environment that encourages all students to participate and take responsibility for group outcomes can further enhance their cooperative skills.

Behavioral Skills

A. Problem Solving

Table 9
The Behavioral Skills of JHS Students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in Terms of Problem-Solving

Problem-Solving	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
1. I identify solutions in challenging Math tasks.	3.23	Agree	High social competence
2. I think of multiple solutions before deciding on one in classwork.	3.15	Agree	High social competence
3. I evaluate the pros and cons of my ideas before acting.	3.13	Agree	High social competence
4. I ask classmates or teachers for advice when I can't solve a problem.	3.27	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
5. I break Math problems into smaller, manageable steps.	2.92	Agree	High social competence
6. I remain focused until I solve a Math-related challenge.	3.10	Agree	High social competence
7. I can adapt if my first solution doesn't work during group activities.	3.14	Agree	High social competence
8. I accept mistakes as part of solving Math problems.	3.22	Agree	High social competence
9. I seek out more information if the task is unclear.	3.13	Agree	High social competence
10. I think creatively to find solutions for Math challenges.	3.15	Agree	High social competence
11. I collaborate with classmates to find better solutions.	3.11	Agree	High social competence
12. I reflect on what I learn after solving Mathematics problem.	3.24	Agree	High social competence
13. I stay calm when solving difficult Math problems.	3.15	Agree	High social competence
14. I consider how my decisions affect my classmates.	3.04	Agree	High social competence
15. I am confident in my problem-solving skills at school.	2.95	Agree	High social competence
Grand Mean	3.13	Agree	High social competence

Table 9 presents the level of social competence of junior high school students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in terms of problem-solving. The statement, *“I ask classmates or teachers for advice when I can’t solve a problem,”* received a weighted mean of 3.27, indicating that students recognize the value of seeking help when faced with challenges. Despite these strengths, some areas require further development like in the statements *“I break Math problems into smaller, manageable steps”* received slightly lower weighted means of 2.92, suggesting that some students struggle with breaking complex problems into simpler parts and may lack confidence in their abilities.

The overall weighted mean of 3.13, with a descriptive rating of “Agree,” suggests that students exhibit strong problem-solving skills. While students generally think creatively and seek more information when a task is unclear, they might benefit from further encouragement to apply these strategies more consistently. These findings indicate that while students demonstrate good problem-solving abilities, they could improve their systematic approach and confidence in tackling problems independently.

B. Respect

Table 10
The Behavioral Skills of JHS Students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in Terms of Respect

Respect	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
1. I treat my classmates the way I want to be treated.	3.23	Agree	High social competence
2. I listen to my teacher even when I disagree with their instructions.	3.04	Agree	High social competence
3. I avoid making fun of my peers’ ideas during discussions.	3.12	Agree	High social competence
4. I respect the opinions of classmates, even if I don’t agree.	3.15	Agree	High social competence
5. I value the effort my teachers put into preparing lessons.	3.20	Agree	High social competence
6. I avoid interrupting my classmates when they are speaking.	3.08	Agree	High social competence
7. I give credit to classmates for their contributions in group work.	3.24	Agree	High social competence
8. I follow school rules and respect the expectations set by my	3.29	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence

teachers.			
9. I avoid judging classmates based on their appearance or background.	3.08	Agree	High social competence
10. I respect my classmates' personal boundaries during activities.	3.25	Agree	High social competence
11. I acknowledge the achievements of my classmates.	3.17	Agree	High social competence
12. I avoid gossiping or spreading rumors about my peers.	3.08	Agree	High social competence
13. I respect different cultural beliefs or traditions in school.	3.23	Agree	High social competence
14. I use polite language when talking to teachers and classmates.	3.18	Agree	High social competence
15. I avoid disrupting the class out of respect for my teacher.	3.15	Agree	High social competence
Grand Mean	3.17	Agree	High social competence

Table 10 exhibits the level of social competence of Junior High School students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in terms of behavioral skills respect. It includes indicators that assess students' respectful behaviors, such as listening to teachers, acknowledging classmates' achievements, and following school rules.

The results show that students exhibit high social competence in terms of respect, with all indicators receiving a rating of "Agree." The statement, *"I follow school rules and respect the expectations set by my teachers"* received a "Strongly Agree" response with a weighted mean of 3.29. However, some areas, like listening to a teacher even when they disagree with their instructions, scored slightly lower with a weighted mean of 3.04. While students generally demonstrate respectful behaviors, there are occasional areas for improvement in their social interactions. The grand mean of 3.17 indicates an overall agreement among students in demonstrating respect.

C. Conflict Resolution

Table 11
The Level of Social Competence of JHS Students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in Terms of Conflict Resolution

Conflict Resolution	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
1. I listen to both sides of an argument before sharing my opinion.	3.23	Agree	High social competence
2. I stay calm when disagreements arise in group activities.	3.13	Agree	High social competence
3. I try to find solutions that work for everyone in group work.	3.23	Agree	High social competence
4. I avoid blaming others during disagreements in group work.	3.13	Agree	High social competence
5. I use "I" statements to express my feelings during conflicts.	3.25	Agree	High social competence
6. I focus on solving the problem instead of attacking the person.	3.23	Agree	High social competence
7. I avoid raising my voice during classroom disagreements.	3.04	Agree	High social competence
8. I can explain my perspective respectfully during a disagreement.	3.11	Agree	High social competence
9. I try to understand the other person's point of view during a conflict.	3.18	Agree	High social competence
10. I am willing to compromise to resolve issues in group work.	3.24	Agree	High social competence
11. I apologize when I realize I am wrong during a conflict.	3.18	Agree	High social competence
12. I encourage open communication to settle disagreements.	3.11	Agree	High social competence
13. I avoid holding grudges after resolving a disagreement.	3.18	Agree	High social competence
14. I help mediate conflicts between classmates when needed.	3.18	Agree	High social competence
15. I follow through on agreements made to resolve conflicts.	3.21	Agree	High social competence
Grand Mean	3.18	Agree	High social competence

Table 11 presents the level of social competence of Junior High School students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in terms of conflict resolution.

The results indicate that students exhibit high social competence in resolving conflicts, with all indicators receiving a rating of “Agree.” The statement, *“I use ‘I’ statements to express my feelings during conflicts,”* received a weighted mean of 3.25, highlighting students' ability to communicate emotions effectively. However, the statement *“I avoid raising my voice during arguments”* received the lowest mean of 3.04, suggesting that students may struggle with maintaining composure in tense situations.

The grand mean of 3.18 suggests that, on average, students agree that they demonstrate good conflict resolution abilities. This means that JHS students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School exhibit a good conflict resolution skills, demonstrating respect and cooperation when dealing with disagreements. However, continued efforts to improve self-control and open communication during conflicts can further enhance their ability to resolve disputes in a more constructive manner.

Intrapersonal Skills

A. Emotional Regulation

Table 12
The Intrapersonal Skills of JHS Students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in Terms of Emotional Regulation

Emotional Regulation	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
1. I stay calm when I feel frustrated during difficult lessons.	3.20	Agree	High social competence
2. I take deep breaths to manage my emotions during exams.	3.21	Agree	High social competence
3. I avoid saying hurtful things when I'm upset with a classmate.	2.96	Agree	High social competence
4. I can recognize when my emotions are affecting my focus in studying.	3.18	Agree	High social competence
5. I find healthy ways to cope with stress from Math activities.	3.11	Agree	High social competence
6. I stay focused even when I'm feeling anxious about an assignment.	3.11	Agree	High social competence
7. I understand why I feel upset during conflicts with peers.	3.15	Agree	High social competence

8. I manage my emotions without taking them out on others.	3.15	Agree	High social competence
9. I avoid letting small classroom problems ruin my day.	3.13	Agree	High social competence
10. I can express my emotions calmly during disagreements on a task.	3.13	Agree	High social competence
11. I recognize when I need to take a break to refocus my emotions.	3.10	Agree	High social competence
12. I forgive myself when I make emotional mistakes in class.	3.18	Agree	High social competence
13. I use positive self-talk when I feel overwhelmed with Math tasks.	3.15	Agree	High social competence
14. I avoid reacting impulsively during group disagreements.	3.11	Agree	High social competence
15. I manage my emotions effectively during stressful group activities.	3.18	Agree	High social competence
Grand Mean	3.14	Agree	High social competence

Table 12 shows that junior high school students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School generally demonstrate high social competence in terms of emotional regulation, with a grand mean of 3.14 and a descriptive rating of Agree.

Students exhibit good emotional management skills, such as staying calm during difficult lessons, managing emotions effectively, and recognizing when emotions impact their focus. They also engage in positive self-talk and seek appropriate coping mechanisms when dealing with stress. Students have a solid foundation in emotional regulation but could benefit from further support.

The data shows that the student respondents have high social competence as revealed by the general weighted mean of 3.14

Intrapersonal Skills

B. Self-Awareness

Table 13
The Intrapersonal Skills of JHS Students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in Terms of Self-Awareness

Self-Awareness	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
1. I understand how my actions affect my classmates.	3.31	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
2. I reflect on my behavior after disagreements in class.	3.22	Agree	High social competence
3. I recognize my strengths and weaknesses in Mathematics.	3.14	Agree	High social competence
4. I can identify my feelings when I succeed or fail in Math tasks.	3.18	Agree	High social competence
5. I know when to ask my teacher for help with a difficult task.	3.14	Agree	High social competence
6. I am aware of how my mood affects my interactions with peers.	3.09	Agree	High social competence
7. I understand the values that guide my actions in school.	3.26	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
8. I take responsibility for my actions during group activities.	3.17	Agree	High social competence
9. I am aware of my personal academic goals and how to achieve them.	3.27	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
10. I recognize patterns in my behavior that affect my performance in Mathematics.	3.20	Agree	High social competence
11. I understand how my classmates and teachers perceive me.	3.25	Agree	High social competence

12. I reflect on how I can improve after making mistakes in class.	3.21	Agree	High social competence
13. I can recognize factors that influence my emotions.	3.10	Agree	High social competence
14. I adjust my behavior based on constructive feedback from teachers.	3.13	Agree	High social competence
15. I understand what motivates me to work hard in Math tasks.	3.20	Agree	High social competence
Grand Mean	3.19	Agree	High social competence

Table 13 presents data on the level of self-awareness among junior high school students at Sto. Domingo Integrated School as an aspect of social competence. It includes various self-awareness indicators, such as understanding emotions, recognizing strengths and weaknesses, reflecting on behaviors, and identifying the impact of actions on others.

Certain aspects, such as understanding actions that affect their classmates, received a high rating of 3.31, indicating strong self-reflective abilities. However, some areas, like awareness of how mood affects peer interactions, scored slightly lower with a weighted mean of 3.09. The students exhibit a high level of self-awareness, with a grand mean of 3.19. This suggests that students generally recognize their emotions, behaviors, and its effect on their social interactions, thus have a high social competence.

C. Flexibility

Table 14
The Intrapersonal Skills of JHS Students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in Terms of Flexibility

Flexibility	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
1. I adapt my plans when unexpected changes occur in group activities.	3.20	Agree	High social competence
2. I handle disruptions in my school routine calmly.	3.13	Agree	High social competence
3. I am open to working with different classmates in group tasks.	3.21	Agree	High social competence

4. I stay positive when my teacher assigns a new way of learning.	3.27	Strongly Agree	Very high social competence
5. I try different approaches when solving difficult math problems.	3.20	Agree	High social competence
6. I remain focused even when the teacher changes the task.	3.17	Agree	High social competence
7. I adapt my behavior to meet the needs of group activities.	3.20	Agree	High social competence
8. I embrace change as a part of school life.	3.13	Agree	High social competence
9. I remain open to feedback from classmates and teachers.	3.18	Agree	High social competence
10. I adjust my role in group work to fit the task at hand.	3.22	Agree	High social competence
11. I accept that others may have different ways of solving problems.	3.23	Agree	High social competence
12. I quickly switch between tasks when needed during class.	3.13	Agree	High social competence
13. I remain calm when plans for group projects don't go as expected.	3.21	Agree	High social competence
14. I adjust my goals if I find them too unrealistic for the given time frame.	3.08	Agree	High social competence
15. I learn from unexpected challenges and apply those lessons in school.	3.18	Agree	High social competence
Grand Mean	3.18	Agree	High social competence

Table 14 presents the level of social competence among Junior High School students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School in terms of flexibility. It evaluates students' ability to adapt to changes, handle disruptions, remain focused, and accept different perspectives.

The results show that students demonstrate high social competence in flexibility, students agreeing to all the statements except for one: *"I stay positive when my teacher assigns a new way of learning"* which received a "Strongly Agree" rating with a weighted mean of 3.27. This suggests that students generally have a good capacity for adaptability. However, there are still occasional areas for improvement, particularly in adjusting goals

when unrealistic for the given time frame, achieving a weighted mean of 3.08. The grand mean of 3.18 indicates that, on average, students agree that they exhibit flexibility in various school-related situations, which implies that they have high social competence.

JHS students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School exhibit a commendable level of flexibility, as reflected in the results. While they generally adapt well to changes and challenges, continued development in their adaptability and problem-solving skills will further enhance their ability to navigate different academic and social situations effectively.

Table 15
Summary of the Level of Social Competence Of the JHS Students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School

Social Competence	Components	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
A. Social Skills	Active Listening	3.10	Agree	High social competence
	Empathy	3.15	Agree	High social competence
	Communication	3.11	Agree	High social competence
	Cooperation	3.17	Agree	High social competence
		3.13	Agree	High social competence
B. Behavioral Skills	Problem Solving	3.13	Agree	High social competence
	Respect	3.17	Agree	High social competence
	Conflict Resolution	3.18	Agree	High social competence
Mean		3.16	Agree	High social competence
C. Intrapersonal Skills	Emotional Regulation	3.14	Agree	High social competence
	Self-Awareness	3.19	Agree	High social competence
	Flexibility	3.18	Agree	High social competence
Mean		3.17	Agree	High social competence
Grand Mean		3.15	Agree	High social competence

Table 15 presents the summary of the level of social competence of the Junior High School students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School.

Based on the results, the students “Agree” to all components across the three domains, which means that the students exhibit a high level of social competence. The Social Skills domain obtained a mean of 3.13; Behavioral Skills, 3.16; Intrapersonal Skills, 3.17. The grand mean of 3.15 further supports that students, in general, possess high social competence. This implies that the students can listen actively, show empathy, communicate and cooperate effectively, solve problems accurately, respect others, resolve conflicts, regulate emotions, and demonstrate self-awareness and flexibility in their daily interactions.

The findings reveal that the JHS students of Sto. Domingo Integrated School are socially competent individuals. Their strong social, behavioral, and intrapersonal skills can contribute positively to their peer relationships and overall well-being. These results highlight the importance of nurturing and continuously developing social competence among students to help them succeed in both school and life.

3. Is there a significant difference in the social competence of JHS students when grouped according to their profile

Table 16
Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Social Competence of JHS Students when Grouped According to Their Profile

Profile	Significance <i>F</i>	Decision	Remarks
Sex	.059	Accept Ho	There is No Significant Difference
Age	.333	Accept Ho	There is No Significant Difference
Grade Level	.008	Reject Ho	There is Significant Difference

Table 16 reveals the significant difference in the social competence of JHS students when grouped according to their profile using Analysis of Variance *F* -test at .05 level of significance.

As can be seen, the significance *F* -values for the profile sex and age of the respondents mentioned in the above table are greater than .05 which resulted to the acceptance of null hypothesis. This statistically indicates that there is no significant difference in the social competence of JHS students when grouped according to their sex and age.

As to grade level, the significance F -value is less than .05 which resulted to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Thus, there is significant difference in the social competence of JHS students when grouped according to their grade level particularly those who are Grade 10 students.

The findings strongly affirm Erikson’s (1968) psychosocial theory, particularly the stage of “**identity vs. role confusion.**” As students reach adolescence, typically between the ages of 12 to 18, they begin to form a clearer sense of self by exploring their identity, values, and social roles. This aligns with the developmental patterns seen in older JHS students, such as those in Grade 10, who are more engaged in social interactions, peer acceptance, and leadership activities. According to Erikson, the increasing importance of peer relationships during this stage makes **social competence a key factor** in helping adolescents navigate the challenges of fitting in and building their identity. Therefore, the progression in social maturity across grade levels not only reflects academic growth but also supports Erikson’s idea that strong social skills are essential for healthy emotional and psychological development in adolescence.

Aligned with the idea of Erikson (1968), as students move up through Junior High School, their social skills tend to grow along with them. This is because they’re not just learning academics but they’re also figuring out how to manage emotions, communicate better, and understand the people around them. Older students like grade 10, usually have more experience dealing with classmates, group work, and even leadership roles, all of which help them become more socially competent. They also start to care more about how they’re seen by others and how they fit into social circles. That awareness, combined with the increasing responsibilities of school and extra curriculums, push them to develop better teamwork and problem-solving skills.

In short, the higher the grade level, the more chances students get to practice and improve their social abilities - making grade level an important part of how they grow socially during these years.

4. What is the academic performance of JHS students in Mathematics?

Table 17
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of JHS Students When Grouped According to Academic Performance in Mathematics

Grades	Frequency	Percentage	Descriptive Rating
90 – 100	40	28.17	Outstanding
85 – 89	31	21.83	Very Satisfactory
80 – 84	39	27.46	Satisfactory
75 – 79	30	21.13	Fairly Satisfactory

Below 75	2	1.41	Did not Meet Expectations
Mean Grade	85	100	Very Satisfactory

Table 17 presents the academic performance of junior high school JHS students in mathematics based on their grade. The 28.17% of the students, got a grade between 90-100, described as “Outstanding” rating. Meanwhile, 27.46% of the students scored between 80-84, categorized as “Satisfactory.” The 21.83% of students categorized as “Very Satisfactory” scored between 85-89, while 21.13% received a “Fairly Satisfactory” rating, with a score of 75-79. Only two students scored below 75, meaning they “Did Not Meet Expectations.”

The overall performance of students in mathematics is Very Satisfactory indicating that a significant number of students shown a strong grasp of mathematical concepts. While the majority performed well, the small percentage of students who scored below 75 highlights the need for targeted interventions to support struggling learners.

These findings shows that mathematics instruction in Sto. Domingo Integrated School is effective, with most students demonstrating proficiency in the subject. However, efforts could be made to further increase the number of students achieving “Outstanding” ratings while addressing the needs of those who require additional support. Strengthening instructional strategies, providing enrichment activities, and implementing remedial programs could help improve overall student performance in mathematics.

5. Is there a significant difference in the academic performance of JHS students when grouped according to their profile

Table 18
Result of the Test of Significant Difference in the Academic Performance of JHS Students when Grouped According to Their Profile

Profile	Significance <i>F</i>	Decision	Remarks
Sex	.000	Reject Ho	There is Significant Difference
Age	.345	Accept Ho	There is No Significant Difference
Grade Level	.568	Accept Ho	There is No Significant Difference

Table 18 reveals the significant difference in the academic performance of JHS students when grouped according to their profile using Analysis of Variance F -test at .05 level of significance.

As shown in the table, the significance F -values for the profile age and grade level of the respondents mentioned in the table are greater than .05 which resulted to the acceptance of null hypothesis. This statistically indicates that there is no significant difference in the academic performance of JHS students when grouped according to their age and grade level.

As to sex, the significance F -value is less than .05, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant difference in the academic performance of JHS students when grouped according to their sex.

The findings further shows that female students in Sto. Domingo Integrated School perform better in mathematics than the male students which affirms the findings of the OECD's (2019) PISA 2018 study, particularly in the context of the Philippines. While PISA 2018 reported that boys generally scored higher than girls in mathematics across most OECD countries, it also highlighted important exceptions, specifically noting that in countries like the Philippines and Jordan, girls outperformed boys. This supports the idea that gender can significantly influence academic performance, and that female students, when given equal opportunities and supportive environments, can excel in traditionally male-dominated subjects like mathematics.

On the other hand, the performance of female students in mathematics at Sto. Domingo Integrated School is in contrast to the findings of the TIMSS 2015 study by Sibanda and Naidoo (2003) on gender differences in South Africa which concluded that there were no significant overall gender differences in mathematics achievement while on Sto. Domingo Integrated School, female students consistently outperform male students in mathematics.

6. Is there a significant relationship between social competence and academic performance in Mathematics among JHS students at Sto. Domingo Integrated School?

Table 19
Result of the Test of Significant Relationship Between Social Competence and Academic Performance in Mathematics Among JHS Students Of Sto. Domingo Integrated School

Social Competences	Significance r	Decision	Remarks
A. Active Listening	.000	Reject Ho	There is Significant Relationship
B. Empathy	.000	Reject Ho	There is Significant Relationship
C. Communication	.000	Reject Ho	There is Significant

			Relationship
D. Cooperation	.000	Reject Ho	There is Significant Relationship
E. Problem Solving	.000	Reject Ho	There is Significant Relationship
F. Respect	.000	Reject Ho	There is Significant Relationship
G. Conflict Resolution	.000	Reject Ho	There is Significant Relationship
H. Emotional Regulation	.000	Reject Ho	There is Significant Relationship
I. Self-Awareness	.000	Reject Ho	There is Significant Relationship
J. Flexibility	.000	Reject Ho	There is Significant Relationship
Overall	.000	Reject Ho	There is Significant Relationship

Table 19 reveals the result of the test of significant relationship between social competence and academic performance in Mathematics among JHS students at Sto. Domingo Integrated School using Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation r -test at .05 level of significance.

Data shows that the significance r -values between social competences and academic performance in Mathematics are less than .05 which resulted to the rejection of null hypothesis. This statistically indicates that there is a significant positive correlation between social competences and academic performance in Mathematics among JHS students at Sto. Domingo Integrated School.

Hence, the students' academic performance in Mathematics are significantly correlated with their social competences namely Active Listening, Empathy, Communication, Cooperation, Problem Solving, Respect, Conflict Resolution, Emotional Regulation, Self-Awareness and Flexibility. Generally, the social competences of the students are significantly influenced their academic performances in Mathematics.

This affirms Perez (2017) discussions on the importance of social skills in the academic development of Filipino students that students with strong social competence can better adapt to challenging subjects like mathematics, as these skills promote

effective communication and problem-solving within group settings. Salazar (2018) also emphasizes that the Philippine education system prioritizes 21st-century skills, including social competence, as part of holistic learning. Collaborative problem-solving in mathematics is cited as a critical example of how students apply these skills in real-world contexts. Similarly, Castillo (2016) explains the role of social competence in improving classroom interactions and academic performance. The article underscores how Social and Emotional Learning activities embedded in the curriculum lead to better outcomes in subjects like mathematics through enhanced peer collaboration.

Findings of this study also affirms Park and Kim (2012) findings in her study titled “Examining the Role of Social Competence in the Mathematics Achievement of Middle School Students”. She found out that students with higher social competence demonstrated better collaboration skills during group work, which positively affected their academic performance in Mathematics. The study on “The Impact of Social Skills on Mathematics Performance Among Junior High School Students in the Philippines” conducted by Reyes et al. (2021) also pointed out that students who exhibited stronger social skills were more likely to engage in group activities, seek help from peers, and effectively communicate mathematical ideas. The study emphasizes the importance of collaborative learning environments and the role of teachers in promoting social interaction among students. Similarly, it affirms the study of Cruz and Bautista (2022) on “Social Competence and Academic Performance in Mathematics of Junior High School Students in the Philippines” which focused on essential social skills such as teamwork, communication, and conflict resolution, assessing how these skills correlate with students’ performance in Mathematics. She cited that developing social competence is vital for improving academic outcomes in Mathematics. Likewise, Caprara et al. (2016) findings reveal that that higher levels of social competence, including skills like cooperation, empathy, and conflict resolution, are strongly linked to improved academic achievement. Also, Leary’s (2017) perspective on social competence, which covers communication, empathy, and collaboration, suggests that these skills can greatly enhance academic performance.

Prevezer and Swift (2018) also emphasize the importance of communication, empathy, and cooperation in fostering a supportive learning environment that promotes better academic outcomes which aligned in the result of the current study. , Gardner’s (2006) Theory of Multiple Intelligences expands the concept of intelligence by including interpersonal intelligence as a crucial factor influencing academic success, underscoring the importance of social understanding and communication in both individual and collaborative academic settings. Dela Cruz’s (2017) work on The Filipino Learner and Social Skills Development reinforces this by emphasizing that communication, cooperation, and teamwork are vital for students’ personal growth and academic achievement, particularly in subjects like mathematics that require collaborative problem-solving. Glover and Brown (2021) longitudinal study supports these findings by showing that students with strong social skills, including communication and teamwork, tend to perform better academically over time. Similarly, Dela Cruz (2018) reveals that students who excel in communication and conflict resolution often build positive peer relationships, which foster a conducive learning environment. Caday and Buenviaje’s (2019) research is likewise aligned with these conclusions, further emphasizing that communication,

cooperation, and peer relationships are key to academic success, especially in challenging subjects like math.

The study by Antolin and Gabriel (2017) on “The Role of Social Competence in Improving Students’ Mathematics Outcomes Through Cooperative Learning” affirms findings on the positive impact of cooperative learning on students’ performance in mathematics. The study concluded that cooperative learning, where students work together in teams to solve problems, significantly enhances their mathematics outcomes. This study provides strong evidence that cooperation, as a key element of social competence, is essential for improving academic performance, especially in subjects that require collective problem-solving like mathematics.

The study conducted by Shao et al. (2023) also shows that students who experienced positive peer interactions were more likely to engage in collaborative learning, facilitating the exchange of problem-solving strategies. These students tended to perform better in mathematics, as their ability to work together and share strategies led to more effective problem-solving. This further reinforces the argument that students with stronger social ties are more adept at tackling academic challenges, particularly in problem-solving scenarios that require collaboration. These studies affirm that problem-solving, as part of social competence, is essential for improving academic performance, particularly in subjects like mathematics.

For students at Sto. Domingo Integrated School, fostering problem-solving skills through collaboration and positive peer interactions is vital for both their academic success and overall development.

Sousa (2017) takes a cognitive approach to understanding learning and emphasizes the significance of emotional intelligence and social competence in academic achievement. Sousa (2017) highlights that managing emotions and building positive relationships are crucial for reducing stress, which can otherwise be a significant barrier to learning. This underscores that emotional regulation is vital for creating an environment conducive to academic success, as it enables students to remain focused and resilient in the face of challenges. Goleman’s (1995) further supports the importance of emotional regulation, arguing that emotional intelligence (EI) is often a more decisive factor in determining success than IQ. Goleman (1995) explains that individuals with higher EI are better equipped to manage their emotions, build relationships, and succeed academically. This suggests that students with strong emotional regulation skills are more likely to maintain focus, manage stress, and navigate the complexities of academic life with greater success. Hatzigianni and Margetts (2018) also reinforce the connection between social competence, emotional control, and academic achievement. Their research suggests that skills like teamwork and emotional regulation help students collaborate more effectively, particularly in challenging subjects like mathematics. By maintaining emotional control, students are better able to understand complex concepts and stay motivated, ultimately leading to higher academic performance. This highlights the critical role that emotional regulation plays in supporting students’ ability to succeed in both individual and group academic tasks. Furthermore, it also affirms with the study “Social-Emotional Competencies and their Effect on Student Performance in Mathematics,”

conducted by Zhao et al. (2022), that students who scored higher in social-emotional competencies, particularly in emotional self-regulation, performed better in mathematics. The research suggests that fostering these competencies can help students manage math-related anxiety and approach mathematical challenges with greater confidence. Zhao's study supports the argument that emotional regulation, as part of social competence, is crucial for overcoming academic challenges and improving student performance. These studies affirm that emotional regulation is a key component of social competence that directly impacts academic achievement. For students at Sto. Domingo Integrated School, developing emotional regulation skills is vital for managing stress, staying motivated, and succeeding academically.

Reyes and Bunagan's (2021) findings also affirms that a respectful environment is a critical aspect of developing social competence among students, particularly in the context of collaborative academic activities. For JHS students, the ability to work effectively with others, express themselves respectfully, and engage with peers and teachers in a supportive manner are all indicators of social competence. Respect not only impacts their academic performance but also enhances their overall social interactions and growth.

Conclusions

This study explored the social competence and academic performance in Mathematics among junior high school students. The findings indicate that the students under study have high social competence and a very satisfactory performance in Mathematics. Further, the study confirms that there is a significant positive relationship between social competence and academic performance in Mathematics. This emphasizes the importance of fostering social skills alongside academic learning to enhance students' success in Mathematics.

Recommendations

1. Educational planners and policymakers must take a more comprehensive review and analysis of the curriculum into consideration to uphold students' liking for schooling. Based on the result, a more engaging and tailored curriculum is needed. There are 76 male students and 66 female students. The highest number of students falls within the 14–15 age group, while the 16–17 age group has the fewest students. Grade 7 has the highest number of students, while Grade 9 has the lowest number. Policymakers should also address issues related to student retention or transfers out in higher grades and ensure that the curriculum remains relevant to both male and female students. A comprehensive review of these factors will help foster a more engaging and supportive educational environment, thus maintaining students' interest in schooling.
2. Since the results of this study indicate a significant positive correlation between social competence and academic performance in Mathematics among JHS students at Sto. Domingo Integrated School, the involvement of parents and other stakeholders should be strongly encouraged. School-based management should encourage maximum involvement from parents and other stakeholders in all school activities and in the

decision-making process to strengthen their level of participation. If this is done, plans and programs for enhancing students' social competence and improving academic performance in mathematics can be realized.

3. The findings of this study show that mathematics instruction in Sto. Domingo Integrated School is effective, with most students demonstrating proficiency in the subject. However, efforts could be made to further increase the number of students achieving "Outstanding" rating while addressing the needs of those who require additional support. Strengthening instructional strategies by utilizing the knowledge gained through teacher participation in training, seminars, and postgraduate studies to provide more creative and innovative instruction. This will help sustain students' positive attitude and interest in the subject and improve their academic performance in mathematics.

4. Guidance and counseling offices, in collaboration with other teachers, must come up with activities that will enhance an optimal level of social competence, where students can demonstrate strength, effectiveness, and creativity, even under pressure. Fostering activities that further nurture these qualities will help maintain and improve their social skills, benefitting both individual students and the broader school community.

5. Since most of the student respondents in this study are in the age group of 14-15, teachers and administrators should strengthen their interest in school for better completion and retention rates. Programs for older and out-of-school youth interested in continuing their education should reach them, providing an opportunity to advance.

6. Other researchers are encouraged to conduct investigations similar to the present study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher made sure that during the conduct of the study, the following ethical concerns were followed to necessitate safe, anti-fraud, deliberate, and careful undertakings in the study:

1. The researcher, through proper communications, asked permission from the Division Office, and other concerned offices for the study;
2. The researcher also acknowledged the Department of Education and the Schools Division of Isabela for allowing her to conduct the study;
3. The researcher informed the respondents of the study through letters and a short orientation to the study. Data and information gathered were treated with utmost respect and confidentiality;
4. The researcher, properly cited gathered information and other relevant studies from authors, books, or any publications through proper citation.

Acknowledgements

The researcher wishes to convey her sincerest gratitude and appreciation to the following who extended their efforts and priceless assistance which contributed to the completion of this study:

Dr. Mai Rani Khristine A. Zipagan, her adviser, for her invaluable guidance and assistance in the preparation of this work;

Mr. John Mark S. Perito, her husband, for his constant encouragement, guidance, and support throughout the entire duration of the research work;

Dr. Bethzaida S. Balingao, OIC Dean of the Graduate School for her continued motivation, which greatly aided in the completion of this study;

Dr. Salome S. Cariño, Dr. Mario Q. Sevilla, and Mrs. Arcely Q. Say, the panelists for their insightful comments and suggestions that enriched the study;

Dr. Mario Q. Sevilla, the statistician, for his valuable statistical assistance;

Her parents, brother, and sister, for their unwavering moral support and encouragement, which brought this work into reality;

The junior high school students who served as respondents of the study, whose cooperation and responses were vital to the realization of this research;

And finally, to Almighty God, to whom the researcher owes her life, strength, and knowledge, for without His continuous blessings and guidance, none of this would have been possible, especially the successful completion of this research endeavor.

REFERENCES

- Antolin, J., & Gabriel, A. (2017). The role of social competence in improving students' mathematics outcomes through cooperative learning. *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*. <https://www.jamp.org>
- Caday, M. C., & Buenviaje, M. L. (2019). The impact of social skills on academic achievement in public high school students in Metro Manila. *Philippine Education Research Journal*. <https://www.philjol.info/>
- Caprara, G. V., Di Giunta, L., Eisenberg, N., Gerbino, M., & Pastorelli, C. (2016). Social competence and academic achievement in adolescents: The mediating role of academic engagement. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*. <https://scholar.google.com>
- Castillo, L. F. (2016). Social and emotional learning in the Philippines. *Philippine Journal of Social Development*.
- Cruz, R. T., & Bautista, J. L. (2022). Social competence and academic performance in mathematics of junior high school students in the Philippines. *Philippine Journal of Educational Research*. <https://www.pje.ph/>
- Dela Cruz, M. J. (2018). Social skills and academic performance of junior high school students in public schools: The mediating role of peer relationships. *Philippine Journal of Educational Measurement and Evaluation*. <https://ejournals.ph>
- Dela Cruz, R. (2017). The Filipino learner and social skills development. *Philippine Normal University*.

- Eccles, J. S., & Harold, R. D. (1993). Parent-school involvement during the early adolescent years. *Teachers College Record*. <https://scholar.google.com>
- Erikson, E. H. (1950). *Childhood and society*. W. W. Norton & Company.
- Erikson, E. H. (1968). *Identity: Youth and crisis*. W. W. Norton & Company.
- Gardner, H. (2006). *Multiple intelligences: New horizons in theory and practice*. Basic Books.
- Glover, J., & Brown, R. (2021). The influence of social competence on academic achievement in middle school: A longitudinal study. *Journal of Educational Psychology*. <https://www.apa.org/pubs/journals/edu>
- Goleman, D. (1995). *Emotional intelligence: Why it can matter more than IQ*. Bantam Books.
- Hatzigianni, M., & Margetts, K. (2018). The role of social competence in enhancing academic achievement in mathematics: Evidence from junior high school students. *Journal of Educational Research*. <https://www.tandfonline.com/toc/vjer20/current>
- Leary, M. R. (2017). *Social competence and learning: A guide for educators*. Routledge.
- NCPIE. (2006). *Parental involvement in education: Research on impact*. National Coalition for Parent Involvement in Education. <http://www.ncpie.org>
- Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2019). *PISA 2018 results (Volume II): Where all students can succeed*. OECD Publishing. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/pisa-2018-results-volume-ii_b5fd1b8f-en.html
- Park, H. J., & Kim, Y. (2021). Examining the role of social competence in the mathematics achievement of middle school students. *International Journal of Educational Research*. Elsevier.
- Perez, M. C. (2017). Social skills and the Filipino learners. *Philippine Journal of Child and Adolescent Development*.
- Prevezer, W., & Swift, D. (2018). *The social skills handbook: Practical activities for social development*. Routledge.
- Republic Act No. 10533. (2013, May 15). An act enhancing the Philippine basic education system by strengthening its curriculum and increasing the number of years for basic education. *Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines*. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2013/05/15/republic-act-no-10533/>
- Reyes, A. P., & Bunagan, M. A. (2021). Influence of classroom environment on math performance among students in Southern Luzon. *Journal of Classroom Interaction and Student Engagement*. <https://www.philjol.info/>
- Reyes, J. M., & Garcia, A. L. (2021). The impact of social skills on mathematics performance among junior high school students in the Philippines. *International Journal of Educational Research and Development*. <https://www.pje.ph/>
- Salazar, M. B. (2018). Philippine educational system and the development of 21st century skills. *Philippine Normal University Journal of Education*.
- Shao, Y., Kang, S., Lu, Q., Zhang, C., & Li, R. (2023). Relationship between peer interactions, motivation, and academic achievement in mathematics. *BMC Psychology*. <https://bmcp psychology.biomedcentral.com>

- Sibanda, D., & Naidoo, J. (2023). Gender differences in mathematics achievement in TIMSS 2015: Evidence from Grade 9 South African learners. *African Journal of Research in Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/18117295.2023.2257968>
- Sousa, D. A. (2017). *How the brain learns*. Corwin Press.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.
- Zhao, Y., et al. (2022). Social-emotional competencies and their effect on student performance in mathematics. *Frontiers in Psychology*.
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.786852/full>